

INFLUENCE OF PRINCIPALS' FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES ON TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN NORTH CENTRAL NIGERIA

BY

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PHD25EAP0020

Being a thesis submitted to the School of Postgraduate Studies, Nasarawa State University, Keffi in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) degree in Educational Administration and Planning

Department of Educational Management

Faculty of Education

Nasarawa State University, Keffi

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Declaration

I hereby declare that this thesis has been written by me, and it is a report of my research work. It has not been presented in any previous application for the Doctor of Philosophy. All quotations are indicated, and sources of information are specifically acknowledged by means of references.

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Certification

The thesis, "Influence of Principals' Financial Management Strategies on Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria," meets the regulations governing the award of Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Educational

Administration and Planning of the School of Postgraduate Studies, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, and is approved for its contribution to knowledge.

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Dedication

I dedicate this thesis to God Almighty for His unfailing love and protection.

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Abstract

The study examined the influence of principals' financial management strategies on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria. To facilitate this study, five research questions, objectives, and corresponding hypotheses were formulated. Literature relevant to the topic was reviewed. This helped to establish the gap filled by the study. A descriptive survey design was used for the study, with a total population of 271,615 (13,536 teachers, 1,116 principals, and 256,963 students) in 3,112 public secondary schools in the North Central States of Nigeria, and a sample size of 663 (213 teachers, 150 principals, and 300 SS 2 students) from 30 senior secondary schools. The questionnaire contained 25 items, was validated by an expert with a validity index of 0.77, and had a reliability index of 0.81. The questionnaires were administered by the researcher and an assistant researcher, and the data were harmonized based on responses and analysis. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while chi-square was used to test the research hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that budget planning, resource allocation efficiency, revenue generation initiatives, internal control measures, and expenditure control significantly influence teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria. It concluded that principals' financial management strategies enhanced teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria. The study recommended, among other things, that school authorities should strengthen structured budget planning processes to ensure teachers have adequate resources and time for lesson preparation and classroom management.

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